

Cyber Ethics, Entrepreneurship, And The Mediating Role Of Knowledge Sharing

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 20, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: July 22, 2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Cyber Ethics , Entrepreneurship, Knowledge Sharing.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12796010</p>	<p><i>This paper improves our understanding of an important imperative for entrepreneurship which is knowledge sharing and commitment to cyber ethics, due to the extent of the risk to that they are exposed to entrepreneurs should understand the importance of cyber ethics when they share knowledge with each other. The purpose of this article is to examine the relationship between internet ethics and entrepreneurship and the mediating role of the exchange of knowledge in the Jordanian customs department. The researchers used a descriptive, analytical approach to analyze and classify data; 296 Valid Questionnaires were used, and a descriptive analytical approach was utilized for data analysis. The "probability sampling method" was applied for data collection. The main findings are that internet ethics affect entrepreneurship and the exchange of information. Also, the exchange of information has an impact on entrepreneurship as an intermediary role through the study.</i></p> <p><i>This study's findings can be used to gain a deeper insight into the workplaces of Jordanian companies and emphasize the valuable role of Cyber Ethics in explaining the employee's behavior in different organizations.</i></p>

Introduction

In light of the development and technological advancement, the need for cyber security has become very urgent, which is also an interdisciplinary field of knowledge. Cyber security has been linked to electronic ethics which are the choices that individuals make when using digital technologies and media via the Internet.

The use of digital technologies and media binds to electronic ethics whereby when individuals use this media, it must be morally bound (Anderson, 2008). Cyber safety consists of actions that individuals take to reduce the risks they may face when using internet-capable technology (Alsegier, 2016). Cyber security includes technical interventions that protect data, identity information, and devices from unauthorized access or harm. Cyber security includes antivirus software, Internet content filters, firewalls, and password protection. Cyber ethics refers to all ethics that affect the behavior of an individual and society together as well as ethics related to modern technologies and software for several years (Capurro, 2000).

Cyber ethics help business leaders to conduct their business easily and also contribute to achieving development and development in their business through adherence to these ethics as it contributes to maintaining their programs that are of the important strategies in the work being responsible for bearing the risks to which the company or organization is exposed. Entrepreneurs always seek to innovate in their business and the development of their products in order to achieve competition between local and global. Therefore, it is necessary to use modern technological technologies, and from here we see the importance of internet ethics for entrepreneurs and the relationship between them (Harris, 2005).

American identity is primarily concerned with entrepreneurship, as it represents the spirit, adventure, and freedom to move between borders, where entrepreneurs have a prominent role in economic development in the past and present, and entrepreneurs play in the development of culture and the ability to keep pace with developments.

Entrepreneurship represents a group of magazines from economics, incentives, management markets, practical opportunity, law, whether it be to companies or individuals, and internal and external organizations in terms of the environment. Entrepreneurship is complex (Fritsch, 2008).

The company can reach success by exchanging knowledge, which is very important between its members, because this contributes to collecting sufficient information in order to make an appropriate decision, and this constitutes an incentive for workers, which makes the employee able to innovate and improve and improve the overall performance of the company or organization (Hessels, 2011)

Entrepreneurs are exchanging knowledge among themselves because of the importance that this exchange brings and the benefit that it gets through this exchange where this generates certain experiences for them to solve problems that occurred with them where they can benefit from the experiences of others. Where this helps them to make a quick and appropriate decision for the company (Jaen et al., 2013).

In this paper, we will study the impact of cyber ethics on entrepreneurship through the mediate role of knowledge sharing .

Literature review

In light of the previous, and for the aim of formulating hypotheses in pursuit of the study's goals, what follows is a brief review of the relevant literature as concerns the fields of Cyber Ethics, Entrepreneurship, and Knowledge Sharing.

Cyber Ethics

Innovation is the culmination of various continuous relationships and interactions, among different organizations and actors and their cooperation and competition. In innovation networks, firms' performance is dependent on their knowledge assets and their skill in organizing the creation, usage and exchange of knowledge in innovation processes (Dolinska, 2012).

These days, ethics has become a pertinent issue when discussing how to do business, with many economists arguing about the need to study the way ethics are transmitted to the businessmen of the next generation, and whether business ethics are derived from education (Rogojanu and Badea 2011).

Wireless devices such as mobile phones, tablets and computers have enabled people to seek information whenever and wherever they need it. People have to be aware of the importance of unethical conduct when they are dealing with information (Hosny and Fatima, 2014). Misused information could be very useful to people who get certain benefits from it, but at the same time it could harm the life of others (Mason, 1986). There is a link between cyber ethics and responsible behavior that is practiced on the Internet. It can be used in the right way or the wrong way, and this can be determined according to the results that may be a big difference (Bhadauria et al., 2010). Some people use the Internet in a false way and behave badly because no one knows their belief, but because of the development in the world browsers may keep their records, so we must beware of that and the behavior must be legal. A positive attitude towards the concept of cyber ethics that was found to be prevalent among internet customers (Jamal et al., 2016).

There is a law governing the virtual world, and this is what some people who do not have the lowest levels of morals do not know where their identity will be recognized and revealed. The fact that some people use the method of deception in order to obtain possessions or the property of others and to spread obscene, mutilation, viruses or malicious codes that offend the user exposes them to legal issues (Marvel and Norcross, 2017). From here, the internet users must be careful and responsible in order not to harm others, cause harm and commit electronic crimes without knowing about them. Therefore, they must be careful not to spread outrageous and related videos, as well as viruses and malicious codes, and that they don't steal others' personal belongings.

Cyber Ethics leads to the formation of guiding principles regarding good and bad, right and wrong, which is linked to the realm of cyberspace. It attempts to perform and adjust basic virtues and values to definite new situations and challenges occurring from cyber society and cyber technologies. Since cyberspace affects all divisions of our society, cyber ethics contains approximately all ethics fields. Also, ethics in cyberspace is interconnected, multi-(cultural, philosophical, religious) and global (Stückelberger and Duggal, 2018).

"Cyber ethics" refers to the code of responsible behavior on the Internet. Just as we are taught to act responsibly in everyday life with lessons such as "Don't take what doesn't belong to you" and "Do not harm others," we must act responsibly in the cyber world as well (Chow, 2011).

Cyber ethics concerns to the code of responsible behavior on the Internet.

Copyrighting or Downloading: Copyrighting, as a form of intellectual property law, is used for the protection of all original authorship works, including artistic, musical, literary, and dramatic works, which include, but are not limited to, movies, music, poetry, novels, and computer architecture and software. Copyright is granted to the author upon the creation of any of any original work (Ramaiah, 2014). Several risks involve this matter, when people are unaware of these things, especially children, as they do not have knowledge about these policies and all they need is download only without knowing what may happen later. Over time, copyrighting, stopped just being about selling a product, but became an art of storytelling, which is rooted in the desires of humans for storytelling (Chartrand, 2008).

Crime and Punishment: The prevailing attitudes amongst the general public regarding crime and punishment shape their view about how the government should intervene following criminal behavior, and are reflected in people's politics concerning the punishment's nature. Various presentations of crime and punishment are constructed with the intent of the opposition of the threat of opposing presentations. (King, 2017). The internet user badly does not think that he will face problems from misuse and lack of commitment to cyber ethics, where

in light of development can track and track the offending person, therefore it must be noted and cautious. (Aggarwal, 2014). Also, one of the critical consequences of employee misbehavior, as internet users, is being led to sabotage behavior which is considered a crime (Shadi and Atan, 2018).

Internet Hacking: There currently exists many different types of threats to information security which have the end result of causing loss of integrity, confidentiality, and availability. Three categories of information threats have been identified by previous literature which include unintentional or accidental, instrumental or contributory, and intentional or deliberate (Afyouni, 2006; Greitzer et al, 2014).

Over the years, there has been a dramatic increase in the incidence of computer hacking. A hacker, in the context of computer security, is someone who searches for security weaknesses in computer systems or networks for the purpose of exploiting them. Hackers are considered a global threat as they use their knowledge in order to gain unauthorized access into computer systems and networks to harm others, cripple systems, gain access to critical information, or to make profits. In addition to personal profits, hackers may also hack into computer systems for the purpose of just having fun or just to prove themselves (Singh and Pandey, 2016). Usually, hacking is by trying to steal the password and the user's confidential information, as well as by sending viruses that shut down sites and confuse computers (Long et al., 2007).

Cyber bullying: The term cyber bullying seems to have been coined in Canada in the year 2000, by an owner of a website which is dedicated to the prevention of traditional bullying (Aboujaoude et al., 2015). The phenomenon of cyber bullying has been defined as "any behavior performed through electronic or digital media by individuals or groups that repeatedly communicates hostile or aggressive messages intended to inflict harm or discomfort on others"(Tokunaga, 2010, p. 278). This occurs a lot in social networking sites and through digital messages and chatting through downloading them to devices and phones, and its user may also be subject to electronic crime (Raskauskas and Stoltz, 2007).

Business systems affect the organization's overall performance and innovative overall performance. The ERP and SCM system helps entrepreneurs innovate in new products. And it must provide means of protection for that.(AL Safadi, 2016). Previous literature has found that the rise of cyber bullying is mainly attributed to the pervasiveness and rapid increase in the presence of "information and communication technologies" (ICT) which permeate the lives of today's youth (Cassidy et al., 2013). It is one of the online risks that that youth face and one that they are highly likely to encounter as it accompanies the expansion of the the "virtual world" (Livingstone et al., 2011).

Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is the ability to identify opportunities and the utilization of which, as done by an individual or a group of people, in order bring benefit to society, and, consequently, success to their organization. This culminates in entrepreneurship being considered the forefront of a country's social and economic development and the creation and distribution of wealth (Kumar et al., 2018). Entrepreneurship is considered starting with new business, entering into new business, and preparing to take new risks through organization, development, and management of new projects, and making sure that these projects will make a profit (Steyaert, 2005). Entrepreneurship contributes to creating new opportunities, this in turn, over time, will help employees to train and gain experience and skill. It also works to provide productive projects for new products, this contributes to improving the standard of living for individuals and the development of technology through innovation as it works to seek community and enhance the self-confidence of the individual through the employment imperative that it provides(Alsafadi,et,al,2020). This will reflect positively on society and its development (Lindgren and Packendorff, 2007).

Entrepreneurial skills can encompass a broad range of various skill sets like technical skills, leadership and business management skills and creative thinking. Because entrepreneurial skills can be applied to many different job roles and industries, developing your entrepreneurial skills can mean developing several types of skill sets. For instance, to be a successful business owner, you may need to develop your business management skills. To build and maintain successful project teams you might need to improve your leadership and communication skills (Ojo et al., 2013).

Entrepreneurship excels the technical skill of entrepreneur, with the technological development and availability of modern computer programs that will help them in the ability to financial analysis, planning and electronic marketing of their products through the use of digital methods where they can study the volume of sales, costs and revenues and measure the performance of this business, in turn, which will enable them to make decisions better and faster (Lee and Hung, 2014, Alsafadi and Altahat ,2021).

While business owners themselves do not need to be expert information technology, they do need to invest in employees or consultants who have that expertise. Retail businesses need point-of-sale (POS) systems that are compatible with mobile payment systems like Google Pay or Apple Pay. It's also important to have a web presence that emphasizes search engine optimization. Likewise, you should have a web developer on staff or to contract with one who has the SEO skills to make sure your online content is being seen by your target demographics (Eckhardt and Shane, 2003).

Websites also need to be mobile-friendly in addition to being desktop-friendly to reach potential customers accessing the site through their smartphones. Technology is widely deployed and entrepreneurs strive to struggle and discover innovation to keep pace with this development through more dynamic and effective strategic planning in order to respond and adapt to these developments and the success of innovations and provide solutions (AL Safad, 2016).

Knowledge Sharing

Knowledge management is a significant factor in organizations striving to improve performance. This is because not only are the practices of knowledge sharing, which include knowledge creation, knowledge sharing, knowledge acquisition, and knowledge retention, positively correlated with each other, but they also are positively correlated with organizational performance as well (Alyoubi et al, 2018).

Previous authors have argued that a competitive advantage is granted to companies who utilize knowledge management practices because they enable companies to act more efficiently, innovatively, and sustainably. Knowledge management help remove resource constraints, and decrease costs as well as enabling companies to create innovative applications of already existing products to stay ahead of their competitors. As such the benefits of knowledge sharing that can be derived by small or medium enterprises (SMEs) have long been documented (Saini, 2013).

Knowledge sharing behaviors have been investigated with great detail in different contexts and designs by researchers around the world, including the United Kingdom, United States, Asia, Europe, and Africa (Caniëls et al., 2017; Ding et al., 2017; Fullwood & Rowley, 2017; Mafabi et al., 2017; Wang and Noe, 2010)

Organizations consider knowledge exchange a good and innovative performance, therefore they support, encourage and motivate internal and external organizations to do so (Gressgård et al., 2014). Knowledge sharing means the exchange of skills, knowledge, experiences and experiences between employees, They It is also important for groups, as it creates competitive advantages within organizations by sharing knowledge among employees (Wang and Noe, 2010) .It is accepted that technology represents one amongst the foremost necessary and quickest ways in which to exchange data in addition. One amongst the benefits of information sharing is that it considerably will increase the knowledge of the person concerned and broadens its horizons, though it's a serious challenge within the field management as a result of some workers tend to resist sharing their knowledge with the remainder of the organization's members.

Knowledge sharing will be a serious challenge within the field of information management occasionally. The issue of sharing data is that the transfer of information from one entity to a different. Some tend to resist the transmission as a result of the concept that knowledge is the property of any property and so it's vital. So as to counter this, people should be confident that they'll acquire data and can gain expertise reciprocal (Stewart, 1997).The way an organization uses knowledge affects its ability to achieve goals and achieve results (Hussein and Çağlara, 2019).

Finally, knowledge must not be kept secret nor knowledge should be made only for elites, as this leads to its non-spreading and reducing its exchange between people and societies. Accustomed support the analysis framework conferred in Fig. 1

The proposed study

Entrepreneurship plays an important role in stimulating innovation in projects, through the constant search for new opportunities, and working to implement them. It contributes to increasing profits, through community participation in important projects. Entrepreneurship is concerned with stimulating coordination between both the production process and the work effort.

The Internet is a vast world that is used in many areas, and the necessary ethics and ethics must be observed while using it, because the Internet has become an extension of the life that members of society live on the ground, and all laws and ethics that are applied on the ground, and acceptance and tolerance of others with different Their cultures

Hence, entrepreneurs must adhere to internet ethics such as taking into account copyrights, to download for other companies, cyber bullying on other companies, and a sense of responsibility towards that, their commitment gives them a good reputation.

What is the mediating role for knowledge sharing in the relationship between cyber ethics And entrepreneurship?

The importance of this study comes from the role that cyber ethics plays and use it within the organization or company in relation to entrepreneurship, knowing that the entrepreneurs of all their businesses are based on the Internet, noting that there are not enough studies for such a topic where researchers went to research this topic because of its importance, especially that Entrepreneurs knowledge sharing with each other.

Research Hypotheses

H₁: There is statistically significant impact between Cyber Ethics and Entrepreneurship

H₂: There is statistically significant impact between Cyber Ethics and Knowledge sharing .

H₃: There is statistically significant impact between Knowledge sharing and Entrepreneurship.

H₄: There is statistically significant indirect impact between Cyber Ethics Practices and Entrepreneurship, through Knowledge sharing as a mediator variable.

Methodology description

The study used a quantitative approach with “survey questionnaires” to give deep exposure of the issues. A survey consisting of the following variables (Cyber ethics, Entrepreneurship and Knowledge sharing) was developed. First, to ensure validity, the instrument (questionnaires) was given to three professors of business to ensure the clarity of the items, generating “face validity”. Feedback from these professors was also applied to explain some items to guarantee they were appropriate for the Jordanian framework, and a pilot survey was applied to the instrument with 15 participants. Then, the researchers distributed 280 questionnaires personally to employees and business leaders in small and medium companies which comprised the study community, and 11 questionnaires were excluded because they were not valid for statistical analysis, meaning that 269 questionnaires were analyzed using the latest version of SPSS software and to achieve the goals of the study and determine the study variables. The “probability sampling method” was applied for this study. The researchers used a descriptive analytical approach to analyze and classify data which depended on a basic descriptive scientific method of problem analysis using statistical analysis.

Results

The distribution of the paragraphs of the questionnaire is displayed in Table 1, while showing which questions correspond to each variable.

Table 1. The distribution of the paragraphs of the questionnaire

Independent Variables (Cyber Ethics)	
Copyrighting or Downloading	Q (1-7)
Crime and Punishment	Q (8-12)
Internet Hacking	Q (13-17)
Cyber-bullying	Q (18-21)
Moderating Variables (Knowledge Sharing)	
Knowledge Sharing	Q (22-31)
Dependent Variables (Entrepreneurship)	
Strategic orientation	Q (32-36)
Commitment to opportunity	Q (37-41)

To measure the level of internal consistency to solve the paragraphs in the questionnaire, the researchers used the Alpha Cronbach coefficient after the researcher developed the questionnaire to cover all dimensions of independent and dependent variables in order to test the study hypotheses that were distributed and configured to the sample individuals.

This was used in order to increase the degree of reliability and reliability of the data collected and verified. Sample responses were distributed according to Likert five-point scale, which indicates the extent of the respondent's approval of the questionnaire paragraphs.

The Internal consistency coefficients: Reliability coefficient (Cronbach Alpha) is displayed in Table 2.

Table 2. (Cronbach Alpha)

Variables	Reliability coefficient
Copyrighting or Downloading	.690
Crime and Punishment	.810
Internet Hacking	.811
Cyber bullying	.699
Knowledge sharing	.880
Strategic orientation	.783
Commitment to opportunity	.739
Commitment of resources	.819
Total	.939

Through Table No. 2, “Cronbach Alpha” was used to test the reliability (internal consistency) of the questionnaire, using (SPSS) by finding the reliability coefficient value, which is, as is shown above, acceptable for this type of study. It appears to us that the percentage of security transactions for the variables is higher than 65%, and this indicates that there is internal consistency between the corridors. 93.9% confirm the legitimacy of the survey in the tested theory.

The the results of regression analysis on the relationship between Cyber Ethics and Entrepreneurship are displayed in Table 3.

Table 3. Cyber Ethics and Entrepreneurship (testing H1)

Model	B	UC Std. Error	Beta	SC T	Sig.	F-value = 100.026(Sig. =0.000) Adjusted R- Square = 0.559
(Constant)	1.390	.191		6.999	.000	As we can observe from the results of Table 3, F-value is statistically significant which means there is a linear relationship between independent variables and a dependent variable. Adjusted R-Square is equal to 0.559 which means the regression estimates approximately 56 percent of the changes on the dependent variable. All t-values are meaningful when the level of significance is on cepercent. The results of coefficients for the impact to cyber ethics dimensions on Entrepreneurship are summarized in Table 3. Therefore, the first hypothesis is confirmed which means cyber ethics influence on Entrepreneurship.
Copyrighting and Downloading	.089	.039	.131	2.119	.029	
Crime and Punishment	.379	.050	.499	8.999	.000	
Internet hacking	.199	.051	.321	5.010	.000	
Cyber Bullying	.399	.019	.381	19.999	.000	

The the results of regression analysis on the relationship between cyber ethics and knowledge sharing are displayed in Table 4.

Table 4. Cyber ethics and Knowledge sharing (testing H2)

Model	B	UC Std. Error	Beta	SC T	Sig.
(Constant)	1.999	.890		11.510	.000
Cultural	.132	.052	.169	3.100	.006
Managerial	.177	.050	.199	3.999	.000
Structural	.221	.051	.310	3.890	.000
Social	.319	.051	.299	7.999	.000

.000 F-value = 51.111(Sig. = 0.000) Adjusted R-Square =0.411

When the value-T ratio is 51.111 and significant for the significance level, the adjusted R-Square equals 0.411, or 41% of independent variables, describing changes in the function through the results of the ANOVA test. Therefore, we conclude that all the values of entrepreneurs T in the samples are statistically significant and therefore the dimensions of Internet ethics greatly affect the exchange of information and the hypothesis that we assumed for the survey is acceptable, H2 received support.

The results of regression analysis on the relationship between knowledge sharing and Entrepreneurship are displayed in Table 5.

Table 5. Knowledge sharing and Entrepreneurship (testing H3)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	
(Constant)	1.829	.310		3.999	.000
Knowledge Sharing	.781	.060	.060	12.111	.000

Adjusted R-Square =0.391

As we can observe from the results of Table 5, Adjusted R-Square is equal to 0.391 which means the regression analysis may describe approximately 39 percent of the changes on the dependent variable. T-value is statistically meaningful when the level of significance is one percent. Therefore, the hypothesis 3 is confirmed and we can conclude that knowledge sharing influences on entrepreneurship.

The results of regression analysis on the relationship between cyber ethics and entrepreneurship, through knowledge sharing (mediator variable), using path analysis test (PLS), are displayed in Table 6.

Table 6. Cyber ethics and entrepreneurship, through knowledge sharing (testing H4)

Hypothesis	Relationship	Std. Error	Beta	t-value	Bootstrapped confidence interval		Decision
					95% LL	95% UL	
					Entrepreneurship Variable	SV-FSC-DC	
	CE-KSE		69.79%				Partial Mediation

Table 6 shows the results of the path analysis where the table shows the value of (LL,UL) confidence period (69.7%) which gives the minimum (LL) and the maximum (UL) as well as the values (VAF) that were greater than (20%) and less than (78%), which indicates that there is a partial impact of the knowledge sharing, that is, there is an impact at the level (0.05) of cyber ethics through the moderator variable (knowledge sharing).

Discussion

The research results confirm the impact of cyber ethics dimensions on Entrepreneurship. Therefore, the first hypothesis (There is statistically significant impact between Cyber Ethics and Entrepreneurship) is assured which means that the relationship between entrepreneurship and cyber ethics was significant and positive, in accordance with Widyani et al, (2020), and in agreement with Bucar and Hisrich (2001). Moreover, the second hypothesis (There is statistically significant impact between Cyber Ethics and Knowledge sharing) was also confirmed, as we can see from Table 4 that cyber ethics greatly affect the exchange of information which is in accordance with Akhavan et al, (2013). Also, the third hypothesis (There is statistically significant impact between Knowledge sharing and Entrepreneurship) was proved based on Table 5, which showed that knowledge sharing influences entrepreneurship, which is in a line with Hafeez et al, (2019). In Addition, the last hypothesis (There is statistically significant indirect impact between Cyber Ethics Practices and Entrepreneurship, through Knowledge sharing as a mediator variable) showed that there is a partial impact from the moderator variable (knowledge sharing), on the relationship between cyber ethics and entrepreneurship, based on the VAF (Variance Accounted For) technique developed by Hair et al, (2014): which posited that VAF <20% indicates no mediation, VAF of 20% -78% indicates partial mediation, and that VAF >78% indicates full mediation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is crucially important for organizations to be very concerned about Cyber ethics. Through study, analysis and statistics, the researchers found that internet ethics affect entrepreneurship and also affects the exchange of information. Also, the exchange of information has an impact on entrepreneurship as an intermediary role through the study. The results from this study propose that Cyber ethics play a vital role in affecting Entrepreneurship and knowledge sharing. So, paying more attention to Cyber ethics can lead to the creation of a healthy environment for Entrepreneurship within any organizations to achieve their goals smoothly.

This study has its limitations, as do all studies. First, the study focused on a few dimensions of Cyber ethics, and as we know there are more dimensions to deal with. Also, The study was applied in Jordan, which a single developing country. Therefore, the results ought to not be measured and generalized to other countries. In spite of these limitations, this study contributed to the information in the scope of management by filling an prevalent gap in the literature.

The researchers advise entrepreneurs to adhere to the ethics of the Internet and take responsibility when using the Internet, especially in light of technological development. It is advised to appoint specialists for this field and when the knowledge is exchanged, the researcher is advised to exchange it with the necessary protections between the entrepreneurs in the Jordanian customs department. It is recommended to carry out further studies to gain more knowledge about Cyber ethics in Jordan and other regions. It is also recommended to enlarge the existing study sample to include more organizations in different branches.

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